

The Assessment of Effects of Migration and Remittances on Nigerian Economy

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ABSTRACT

The study focuses on the examination of the influence of migration and remittances on Nigerian economy over the years. The authors reviewed and examined the positive and negative effects of migration in Nigeria. Expository approach involving tables were employed in the examination. The study confirmed the fact that there are positive and negative effects of migration in Nigeria but asserted that the negative effects outweigh the positive in view of the large proportion of Nigerian quality human capital outside Nigeria and also the large proportion of migrants in Nigeria who also remit a large proportion of their income to their home economies. It was also inferred from the study that if adequate working condition and environment exist and Nigerians migrants return, their contribution would have greater effect on the economy than mere remittances. On this basis the authors made the following recommendations among others: revamping both the rural and urban environment, restructuring social amenities; upgrading and maintenance of infrastructural requirement of the society; insecurity and frequent crisis such as group agitations, religious disharmony, crimes, Boko Haram insurgence among others must be addressed; condition of service for all categories of workers at the local, state and federal levels need to be urgently harmonized; good atmosphere for operation cum the materials required by the academics, doctors, nurses, lawyers, architects, economists among others must be provided to enable them put in their best.

Keywords: Assessment, effects, economy, migration, remittances

INTRODUCTION

All over the world, there has been frequent movement of people from place to place. In recent times some move just for holidays, sight-seeing and experiencing climatic condition, cultural pattern and perception of life in other countries. Nevertheless, many people migrate to other areas and permanently settle to work or engage in any means of earning a living and occasionally visit home countries. United Nations (2009) points out that 215 million people which is 3 percent of the world population are residing in countries outside their countries of birth. Nigeria as a country is not left behind in the various motive of movement to other countries of the world. National Bureau of Statistics (2010) articulated that Nigeria is the most populous nation in Africa with a population estimate of 163 million and with a poverty level of 70%. Prior to and since after independence many Nigerians have resorted to internal and external migration with the motive of seeking a better living environment and means of livelihood.

Some Nigerians especially the rich class often move to other countries just for visiting, sight-seeing, holiday, business, schooling, conferences, medication among others. Mohapatra et al (2010) points out that political problem, internal conflicts and trafficking are relevant causes of international movement, but out of

ten persons, nine migrate due to economic reasons. There are many reasons attributed to frequent traveling and migration to other countries by Nigerians. The level of social facilities in Nigeria such as hospitals, education centres and the entire environments are below the demands and expectations of many Nigerians. In their study, Uma et al (2013) asserted that the occasional political, community clashes and religious upheavals in Nigeria have significantly compel urban-rural, rural-urban and international migration. In addition, the search for better income yielding ventures or white-collar jobs by school leavers, graduates, artisans and the desire to benefit from urban environment and social facilities that are deficient in the rural areas have contributed to incessant migration. In related view, Hughes and Kroechler (2008) articulated that migration originated from two relevant factors known as the push and pull factors. Dwellers in a place are motivated to leave an area due to the push factor while the fascinations to choose a place for settlement are referred to as the pull factor. There have been high tendency for people to opt to satisfy the push factor in Nigeria because of poor economic situation, poor environment, poor working condition, poor remuneration, low degree of application of the rule of law, insecurity, social vices amongst others. This is because the leaders of the country have not been able to effectively improve the economy in such a way as to have all that is required to promote living standard. The attention given to the institutions like schools, tertiary institutions and training centres have not been sufficient to encourage many Nigeriansto have trust on the quality of the products and as such prefer patronizing other countries, hence you see many Nigerians in Ghana, South Africa and European countries pursuing education. It has been reiterated that insecurity of life and property due to incessant insurgence, religious crisis and soon have compel many Nigerian to migrate to other countries. Besides, inability to industrialise has left abundance resources unemployed, thereby leaving idle land, raw materials, labour among others grossly underutilized.

Man as a rational and irrational being is always willing to respond to situations. Migration has become one of the ways taken by Nigerians to seek for unsatisfied circumstances in its domestic home. Rural dwellers are frequently moving to urban places searching for non-available better job opportunities, social facilities, training centres, good housing, medical centres among others. Both rural and urban

dweller are also migrating to other countries of the world looking for better environment devoid of the harsh situations inherent in Nigeria for economic activity. Hence, you have Nigerians virtually in all parts of the world.

International Organization for Migration (2013) showed that the number of Nigerian migrants living outside Nigeria rose from 1.9 million in 2004 to 3.4 million in 2012. It was shown by UNHCR (2009) that the total number of Nigerians who sought for asylum in different foreign countries were respectively 19,407 in 2003, 10,464 in 2005, 10,148 in 2007 and 15,022 in 2008. In literature, various studies such as Rena (2008), United Nations Global Migration Group (2015), UN Department of Economic and Social Affairs (2012), Mahapatra et al (2010) .amongst others have articulated the beneficial and non-beneficial effects of migration given its negative effect on developing economies with respect to loss of human capital or labour force and positive effect due to remittances. Many studies by authors such as Anyanwu and Erhijakpor (2010), Ajayi et al (2009), Gupta et al (2007), Adams and Page (2005), Lachaud (1999) and Adams (1991) have shown that remittances play significant role in reducing various types of poverty in developing countries and also encourage economic activity. This view of remittance is not applicable to all migrants. Study by Nwosu et al (2012) asserted that remittance vary significantly by the country of resident by the migrants and it also depends on the education level of migrant before migration, type of work engaged and macroeconomic condition in the migrant country of resident.

Undoubtedly, one important actions of the Nigerian migrants who have properly settled is that they often remit money back home, help others to join them and support the education of relations and family members. Others also remit reasonable money for construction of houses and investment. They help in empowering people. The World Bank data showed that Nigeria had \$1, 392 billion remittances in 2001 and in 2011; it rose to \$10.681 billion which is a significant increase. It equally showed that remittance contributed 5% to gross domestic product in 2011. But it is obvious that many migrants are professionals/experts in medicine, engineering, education, entrepreneurship, sciences and so on. These caliber of migrants usually leave with their expertise, capital, talents and ingenuity to settle in other regions of the world, thereby, denying a

developing economy of the impact of such desirable role expected at home to support development efforts. Given the recent discourses on the positive and negative effects of migration and remittances, most studies focused only on either positive or negative aspect of either remittance or migration, but in this study, it is our intention to review migration vis-a-vis remittances in Nigeria with a view to proffer policy implications needed to regulate migrations and discourage brain-drain. In this respect, the paper is streamlined thus: section two is the review of literature, section three is an over-view of the effects of migration; an over-view of the effects of remittance is the section four while section five is the way forward and conclusion.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

There have been series of issues, studies on migration and remittances over the years. Various studies support positive effects while others oppose to it. In this section, it is our intention to examine both theoretical and empirical literature. There is movement of factors of production from one region to the other due to migration. In his view Myrdal (1957) articulated the experience of less developed countries emanating from migration which involves chains of causes and effect that he likened to the vicious circle of poverty. The effects are referred to as backwash and spread effects. It presupposes that when people in underdeveloped nations migrate, they usually leave with their expertise (human capital), physical capital (tools, cash), goodwill among others. This action creates imbalance with respect to employment, decline of income and output usually produced by the migrants while at home. It is usually not easy to bring equivalent resources to replace all taken away by migrants. This contractionary effect impacts adversely to underdeveloped economy. This is the backwash effect which is the negative experience of a locality due to migration. On the contrary, the migrants settled at a place with all the factors of production and then contribute to output, income and employment of the resident economy which is spread effect. The expansionary effect of skilled migrants in an area has expansionary effect which remittance may not cover up the effects created at the home economy, if and only if the remittance is immediate but it is not. So, underdeveloped economic development is retarded by the extent to which its professional migrates.

Migration is perceived to originate from the push and pull factors (Hughes and Kroechler, 2008) It has been

reiterated that the push factor which is the driving force for people to leave an area is stronger in underdeveloped nations due to bad governance, poor economic and social environment. Hence, you see incessant rural-urban movement and forceful desire to travel outside the country by Nigerians. This is a major cause of brain drain in Nigeria. This made Silva (2007) to pinpoint that regular brain drain syphon skill manpower of developing countries leading to loss of human capital at some costs such as training and education costs and loss of productivity which reduces the aggregate gross domestic product. Hence, brain drain is viewed as international transfer of productive inputs in form of human capital lacking in a region which is not accounted for in the balance of payment statistics. This is reflected in UNTAC estimate that highly trained African migrants age between 25-35 who usually travel abroad has a monetary value of \$184, 000 at 1997 price (Rena, 2008; Kartz, 2000)

In their study, Funk et al (2017) posit that the level of migration and asylum seekers have raised the burden on migrant countries and so compelled European Union's interest in tackling the root cause and strengthening third world nations migration management efforts through improved cooperation in order to lower the influx. This new intention is based on the ground that increased development aid in the less developed economies will lessen the inclination to migrate to other countries. This has also lead to adoption of cooperative efforts regarding border control and readmission; hence development support of European Union (EU) is now linked to cooperation with respect to migration management. The issue is that there is a shift of articulated European Union Treaties from primary objective of poverty alleviation which may counter economic interest of third countries. There is this believe by EU that increased development of third nations will reduce migration but it may not be so. However, European Union has adopted new approach perceived to be more rewarding which include work/visa scheme, trade agreements or lessening remittance cost; increased support on governance aid considered as a more effective means of lowering migration and putting in place more legal channels for migration so as to constrain those illegal business.

Knoll and Sherriff (2017) in their study were concerned about the rising population of refugees and migrants seeking for protection in Europe due crisis

and wars, clashes, disorder, poverty in Syria, Middle East and Africa disagreements which brought some pressure in Europe. Hence, European states are concerned with battling with this problem outside Europe through cooperation with non-European countries. This led to revamping of level of aids and European Development policy priorities in order to surmount the new trend of influx of people from other parts of the world. The case study focused on the aid responses by five countries which are: Denmark, the European Union institutions, Germany, the Netherlands and Sweden. And also the effect of changes in policy frameworks, strategies, tools, allocation yardstick and practices of programme would impact on the use of Official Development Assistance (ODA). The national budget have shown higher reallocation to meet with the cost situations and reduction in long term development aids earmarked for supporting and development of other countries. Earlier study of microanalysis of migration recounted various motives while migrant workers send money back home. For instance Lucas and Stark (1985) study in Botswana asserted that the two motivations to send money back home are pure selflessness and outright self-interest. The latter is mainly to acquire durable assets such as land, housing and other personal interests while the former is strictly to improve the lives of family members, relations and friends. In each aspect of the two areas migrants remit money, it is because he can afford it and knows the poor living status of those left behind at domestic economy.

Other authors such as Higgins et al (2004), El-Sakka and McNabb (1999), Straubhaar (1986) see remittance to be influenced by variation of macroeconomic variable such as interest rate in domestic economy vis a vis resident of migrant workers. Exchange rate has greatly influence remittance in Nigeria. For instance at moment in Nigeria in which exchange rate is over three hundred and twenty naira (₦320) per dollar, migrant workers remittances, besides helping family members do have a large amount of naira after exchange foreign for investment and acquisition of costly land property in any part of the country. It has been confirmed by a study of Egypt by El-Sakka and McNoabb (1999) that these two macroeconomic variables exchange rate and interest rate differentials play significant role in the desire and motivation to remit through official channels.

In spite of the views of that remittance inflows impacts positively on economic growth, but empirical

findings from Singh et al (2009), Barajas et al (2009), World Bank (2006), Spatafora(2005), IMF, 2005, contradict this view as only little evidence was found. Various views have been articulated about the effects of remittance on one economy or the other such as lowering of work efforts on the part of households who receive remittance and consequently lessen long-run growth (Azam and Gubert, 2006; Chami et al, 2003); stimulate growth because of its improvement of financial access and financial development (Gupta et al 2007; Toxopeus and Lensik, 2007); raising income level of the poor subsection of the economy and not necessarily the growth of the entire economy amongst others. However, Mahapatra et al (2010) posit that still there is inconclusive outcome of effect of remittance on growth mainly because of the difficulty of separating the cause from the effect. Many individual would not have left home economy if not some causative factors like natural disaster, war, political turmoil and so on to other nations of the world.

AN OVER-VIEW OF THE EFFECTS OF MIGRATION

The increased migration in Nigeria has impacted in different ways to the development of Nigeria economy. The level of Nigerian experts in other country of the world is a thing to worry about. How many Americans are in Nigeria? This means that there is something happening in the countries that are detested by Nigerians. The table below shows the Nigerian migrants outside Africa.

Table 1: Estimate of Nigerians Living outside Africa 1989-2004

Country	Year	Population
Italy	1989	3, 575
France	1999	1, 425
UK	2001	88, 380
Canada	2001	10,425
Austria	2001	2, 913
Australia	2001	1,783
Greece	2001	2, 021
Ireland	2002	9, 225
Germany	2002	16, 183
Netherlands	2003	4, 564
Belgium	2004	1, 636
US	2004	160, 000
Total		302, 130

Sources: OECD 2006 & <http://www.migrationinformation.org>

Just as many Nigerians are resident outside Africa, so many are in countries within Africa. Some Nigerians outside are illegal migrants and their number not included in the above information. Nevertheless, a large proportion of Nigerians are desperately yearning to leave the country. This situation has created a vacuum which remittance may not cover up. Many of these Nigerian are highly educated and experts in their field of studies. Disgustingly, the incessant industrial actions or trade disputes, especially in the social and economic sector where education falls has witnessed highest level of industrial strike. Since 1970s there have been series of trade disputes due to one agitation or the other. Central Bank of Nigeria (1998) states that out of 199 trade disputes in 1994, involving 1, 541, 146 workers led to loss of man-days of 234, 307, 748. Many Nigerians' bright minds resort to leaving the country at those periods. Our leaders have not

learnt from this situation and have allowed the recurring of industrial disputes. In recent time, the Academic Staff of Universities Union (ASUU) embarked on strike due to inability of the federal government of Nigeria to keep and fulfil agreements. This was followed by the Resident Doctors trade dispute, leading to the collapse of medical and health institutions. The environmental situation of workers, lack of infrastructure for performance and coupled with poor condition of service have always compel many professional to migrate out of the country. The gains of migration in consideration of the remittances cannot be whole regarded as being the best for a developing economy. The level of gross domestic product is lessened by migration of productive labour. This means to minimize migration, Nigeria has to adopt and borrow a leaf from those countries settled by Nigerians

Table 2 Showing Nigerian emigrants' major countries of destination 2010 & 2013

Countries of Destination	2010			2013		
	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total
Benin	22, 691	14, 345	38,036	26,680	15,895	42,575
Burkina Faso	1, 662	1, 898	3, 560	1, 719	1, 963	3, 682
Cameroon	66, 628	47, 923	114, 551	67, 529	48, 092	115, 621
Canada	8,877	9, 683	18, 560	9, 231	10, 094	19, 325
Cote d' Ivoire	21, 566	20, 863	42, 429	22, 363	21, 398	43, 761
Finland	1, 192	258	1,450	1, 509	335	1, 844
Gabon	14, 866	5, 368	20, 234	16, 798	5, 981	22, 779
Ghana	17, 190	13, 222	30, 412	18, 385	13, 995	32, 380
Germany	16, 146	6, 285	22, 431	16, 297	6, 390	22, 687
Greece	2, 719	1, 083	3, 802	2, 798	1, 137	3, 935
Ireland	5, 959	7, 595	13, 554	7, 951	10, 589	18, 540
Italy	13, 611	21, 486	35, 097	21, 154	26, 919	48, 073
Netherland	3, 607	2, 745	6, 352	3, 898	3, 104	7, 002
Niger	10, 153	9, 569	19, 722	10, 315	9, 747	20, 062
Saudi Arabia	8, 962	4, 695	13, 657	9, 745	4, 933	14, 678
South Africa	13, 043	2, 884	15, 927	15, 249	3, 410	18, 659
Spain	22, 291	13, 968	36, 259	21, 976	14, 909	36, 885
Sudan	8, 364	7, 850	16,214	7, 886	7, 389	15, 275
Sweden	2, 106	891	2, 997	2, 461	1,176	3, 637
Switzerland	2,138	835	3, 073	2, 367	1, 084	3, 451
Togo	8, 958	7, 082	16, 040	9, 046	7, 137	16, 183
UK&N Ireland	72, 498	75, 961	148, 459	89, 193	95, 121	184, 314
USA	136, 420	106, 932	243, 352	141, 364	110, 808	252, 172

Source: UNDESA (2014); SIHMA (2014)

Nigerian migrants have chosen both African and non-African countries as places of settlement. Total migrants outside Nigeria are so many and the accurate figure yet to be arrived at because of illegal migrants who cannot easily make their biodata available.

However, International Organisation for Migration (IOM, 2009) migration profile and World Bank (2010) report on Nigeria remittance pointed that Nigerian emigrants' total number ranges between 836, 832 and 1, 041, 284. In some nations female migrants

out-number male and vice-versa. The dominant countries Nigerian migrants reside in 2010 and 2013 respectively are USA (243, 352; 252, 172) and UK & North Ireland (148, 459; 184, 314), in each, female are more in population while in Africa the concentration of Nigeria in Cameroon in 2013, stood at 115, 621, followed by Cote d' Ivoire with Nigerian migrants of 43, 761. Virtually every country of the world has a Nigerian living in it. Notwithstanding the high population of Nigerians in other countries, many Nigerian are still eager to leave. However, it is

obvious from the table that total male population migrants outside the country are higher than the female and there has been regular increase of migrants every year.

Migrant strategy through Asylum Seeking

Just with the desire to leave Nigeria, many have decided to sake for shelter and safety in other countries of the world when Nigeria is not witnessing any civil war. Table 2 shows the different nations Nigerians have sought for settlement over the years.

Table 3 Showing Nigerian Asylum-seekers in Various Countries, 2000–2008

Country	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008
Australia	390	1,047	1,432	1,849	1,828	880	421	394	535
Canada	800	790	828	637	589	591	685	760	765
France	463	571	884	1,252	1,572	976	434	446	462
Germany	420	526	987	1,051	1,130	608	481	503	561
Greece	14	33	184	444	325	406	391	390	746
Ireland	3,405	3,351	4,050	3,110	1,776	1,278	1,038	1,028	1,009
Italy	47	388	594	722	930	536	0	1,336	5,673
South Africa	114	223	3,244	4,550	1,058	775	712	904	16
Spain	843	1,350	1,440	1,688	1,029	726	632	680	808
Switzerland	226	289	1,062	480	418	219	209	310	988
United Kingdom	835	870	1,125	1,110	1,210	1,230	940	905	970
United States	58	50	73	99	82	59	162	165	177
Others	1,207	1,638	2,249	2,415	2,326	2,180	2,189	2,327	2,312
Total	8,832	11,236	18,152	19,407	14,273	10,464	8,294	10,148	15,022

Source: UNHCR (2009).

From the above table, the topmost countries, Nigerian citizens have sought for asylum is in Ireland, United Kingdom, Canada, Spain and Italy. From 2000-2008 was relatively calm in Nigeria as it was devoid of civil war except occasional political crisis, boundary disputes, Niger Delta Militia disturbances, religious crisis/Boko Haram insurgency in the north, kidnapping and armed robbery among others. The data show high degree of dissatisfaction of many citizens living in Nigeria. Besides, the level of insecurity of life and property, and high level of unemployment given the fact that Nigeria has not developed industries capable of engaging job seekers

and also there is no policy on birth control. The high rate of population growth rate is not supported with social facilities, infrastructure and employment opportunities that can absorb school leavers.

Furthermore, the disregard of agriculture and imbalance in the economy in respect of the rural and urban areas environmental disposition have continuously push rural inhabitants to look for greener pasture either in the urban or outside the country. Consequently, many Nigerian are willing to migrate to other countries in any way possible, be it legal or illegal.

Table 4 Showing Nigerian Refugees in Countries of Resident 2009-2013

Countries	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013
Australia	88	101	106	116	132
Austria	173	228	288	315	346
Cameroon	2,873	2,873	3,223	3,223	7,459
Canada	2,962	2,873	3,608	3,990	4,441
France	658	726	794	889	988
Germany	2,640	2,601	2,667	2,833	720
Ireland	766	777	706	540	477
Italy	2,154	2,200	2,369	2,964	4,638
Netherlands	205	203	216	213	225
Niger	-	-	-	-	8,385
Norway	46	65	93	109	176
Sweden	93	124	147	178	257
Switzerland	61	66	83	92	113
United Kingdom	1,370	1,044	1,089	1,166	1,244
United States	809	719	686	719	733
Others	681	742	1066	674	1,280
Total	15,609	15,640	17,141	18,026	31,614

Sources UNHCR (2014); SIHMA (2014)

Nigerians at different period have sought for settlement in various countries of the world. These include both skilled and unskilled. The increase has been conspicuous in Cameroon, Canada, Italy, and United Kingdom. The highest and most recent is in Niger because of the incessant insurgence in the northern part of Nigeria. Few of the countries have a common boundary with Nigeria and as such very easy for Nigerians to cross over. In addition to this, it can be inferred that there are Nigerians in each of the country not captured in the data. One wonders why this regular migration to other countries of the world. The reasons are not far-fetched because the on-going crisis in Nigeria since over five years ago has stimulated many Nigerian to look for a serene and better living condition outside the country. It can equally be seen from the angle of high cost of doing business and high level of corruption in the country has lessen peoples' confidence in living in the country and as such many prefer to seek for shelter in other counties. It can equally be pointed that serious and unabated revamping of the conditions of Nigerians is yet to commence in spite of good policies. High

income inequality as seen in the income of senators in Nigeria vis-à-vis other Nigerian workers who obtain same goods in same market is really worrisome. Quite disheartening is that many Nigerians such as teachers and other artisan affected by irregular power supply are willing to accept menial jobs in neighboring countries and European countries if given any slight opportunity. The absence of over 97, 000 people categorised as refugees lessen the gross domestic product given the fact that even if remittance is done, it cannot be commensurate with their contributions in Nigeria.

Immigrants in Nigeria

Nigeria has at different periods harbor people from other countries. The total number of immigrants in Nigeria according to UNDESA (2010) is 1, 127, 668. This is about 0.7 percent of 173, 6 million population of Nigeria (IOM-Nigeria, 2014). These immigrants came from both African and non-African countries. Table 3 shows exclusively West Africa migrants residing in Nigeria from 1975-2013.

Table 5 Estimate of West African migrants living in Nigeria, 1970-2013

Country	1970	1975	1980	1984	1991	2010	2013
Ghana	129, 872	312, 904	511, 859	680, 384	78, 706	158,987	176,493
Mali	85, 003	92, 136	87, 221	112, 970	56, 471	114, 071	126, 631
Gambia	30, 600	38, 979	49, 680	52, 134	2, 754	5, 563	6, 176
Sierra Leone	28, 000	29, 112	38, 190	43, 458	1, 623	3, 279	3, 640
Togo	19, 021	26, 989	25, 908	29, 003	48, 993	98, 965	109, 862
Benin	9, 981	15, 767	27, 103	29, 979	100, 939	203, 898	226, 349
Cote d' Ivoire	3, 879	5, 721	8, 931	10, 432	1, 845	3, 728	4, 138
Burkina Faso	45, 890	52, 732	65, 579	72, 328	3, 515	7, 101	7, 883
Liberia	6, 980	5, 789	6, 998	8, 547	8, 175	16, 512	18, 330
Senegal	2, 542	3, 381	3, 920	5, 468	2, 009	4, 058	4, 505
Total	361, 768	584, 030	825, 389	1, 044, 703	305, 030	616, 162	684,007

Source: Arthur (1991); UNDESA (2014); SIHMA (2014)

It is not out of place that just as Nigerians migrate to other countries of the world, people from other part of the world also immigrate to Nigeria. Many citizens of countries in West Africa have settled in Nigeria in the quest for security and economic reasons. Often times this influx of labour compete with indigenous labour. Just as Nigerians in Diaspora remit money to Nigeria so also do these immigrants. From 1980s to 2013 Nigeria has witnessed great inflow of immigrants. This can be attributed to the relative better living standard and tranquility obtainable in Nigeria then and low crime rate unlike the way it is now. The population of immigrant shave contributed to the pressure on the facilities in Nigeria. Nigeria has on different periods accepted to play brotherhood roles by supporting and assisting neighboring countries in crisis. The openness of boarders to West African states made easy movement of labour within the region. It can be inferred that given the population of Nigeria in relation to the other West African countries, the number of Nigerians in West African countries far outweigh the total immigrants from West Africa. A question worthy of asking is that the vacuum created by Nigerian migrants, is it covered by immigrants? Well, it is difficult to say yes or no except when having handy facts and figures. It is difficult to have same quality of immigrant labour commensurate and compensatory to migrant ones that have left Nigeria at the period under consideration.

From the foregoing, it is quite obvious that a good proportion of the Nigerian citizens are resident outside Nigeria. This presupposes that there are some factors strongly pushing people at all times to seek for good living environment and working condition outside the country. Disgustingly is the fact that many

Nigerian leaders frequently travel in those countries resident by Nigerian migrants and cherish the place but unable or unwilling to introduce those things that make those places desirable into Nigeria. Sadly to note is that some of our leaders derive joy in engaging in selfish emulative consumption from other counties but yet to adopt emulative economic restructuring and transformation capable of alleviating poverty. In addition, it is boggling and disheartening that none of the leaders have been able to reduce or tackle poverty to an insignificant level in spite of all beautiful programmes, policies and strategies put in place, instead situations prevail that perpetuate poverty in the country.

An over-view of the effects of remittance

Many scholar have the conviction that migration gives rise to inflow of resources into a domestic economy of a migrant, which is referred to as positive effect of migration while others pinpointed the opposing view of the denial of the migrants' home economy of the scarce capital resources needed for development. For instance, World Bank (2008) points out that in sub-Saharan Africa, a total migrants' remittance of \$10.8 billion which is 1.6% of gross domestic product was made in 2007. Ajaiyi et al (2009), in their study of 38 Sub-Saran African countries asserted that international remittances have played desirable roles in raising living standard of the people.

Mbuto (2010) posits that in Nigeria, total remittances experienced average growth of 121% from 2004 to 2006 and at the same period, the average contribution of remittances to gross domestic product was about six time higher when compared to all export income excluding that of oil. Ighomwenghian (2017) reported that remittances to Nigeria in 2016 stood at \$19

billion placing Nigeria as one of the top six receivers for the period although below last year remittance of \$21 billion. The fall in remittance was attributed to fall in oil prices which led to tighter capital controls and government managed exchange rate policy that gave room for black marketers' premiums in foreign exchange markets. Consequently, a large proportion of formal remittance went into informal hands. It was equally noted that remittances in developing countries fell again which has not happened for about 30 years period and as such many remittance-receiving developing countries experienced sharp fall. In Africa, Nigeria is rated highest in the contribution of remittance as a percentage of GDP of 19% in 2016. However, in this section; it is our intention to examine remittance into Nigeria with a view to take proper stand of effects of migrant remittance on Nigeria.

Surprisingly, in spite of these inflow. Poverty in Nigeria has not fallen as poverty is estimated at 70% in Nigeria. It implies that the proportions of Nigerians that benefit from remittances are insignificant proportion of the population.

Table 6 Showing outflow and inflow of remittances (in US \$million) 2009-2011

Year	Outflow (in US \$ million)	Inflow of remittances (in US \$ million)
2009	47	9,585
2010	48	10,045
2011	-	10,681
Total	95	30,311

Source: World Bank (2014)

Remittances inflow and outflow in Nigeria cannot be ignored in view of the large number of immigrants in Nigeria and a good proportion of Nigerian migrants all over the world. The data above show that outflow of remittance far outweigh inflow. This is clear and can be attributed to dominant explorers of Nigeria oil to be expatriates and also many Nigerian students in other countries are sustained from Nigeria. This is not a very healthy situation for Nigeria who supposed to improve and equip its tertiary institutions but would prefer patronage of foreign schools at the expense of domestic institutions.

Table 7 Showing personal remittances received in Nigeria as percent of gross domestic product (GDP), real GDP and exchange rate 2000-2015

Year	Real GDP (₦)	Remittances %	Exchange Rate
2000	412,332	3.001	102.11
2001	431,783.2	2.643	111.94
2002	451,785.7	2.045	120.97
2003	495,007.2	1.571	129.36
2004	527,576	2.587	133.5
2005	561,931.4	13.043	132.15
2006	595,821.6	11.643	128.65
2007	634,251.1	10.823	117.96
2008	672,202.6	9.229	130.75
2009	718,977.3	10.838	158.5
2010	776,332.2	5.35	153.13
2011	834,000.8	5.007	158.27
2012	888,893	4.457	157.36
2013	63,218,720	4.039	167.38
2014	67,152,790	3.664	169.68
2015	69,023,930	4.378	197

Source: CBN (2015), <https://dataworldbank.org/indicator/BX.TRF.PWKR.DT.GD25/location>

The data above show the extent remittances have contributed to the GDP over the years. The period 2003 to 2009 excluding 2008 showed a two digit percentage contribution. The fluctuation is related to the exchange rate and the economic situation prevalent in the country at the period. It can be inferred that remittances have been impacting on Nigeria economy to an extent given the fact that exports of some none oil products have not contributed up to the amount of remittances. But it can equally be pointed out that the impact of all the professional Nigerians in Diaspora functioning in Nigeria would have impacted more on the economy than the remittances effect. Disgustingly is that the outflow or remittances from immigrants in Nigeria far outweigh what comes into Nigeria as shown by table 6. This is because some of the functional manufacturing and services provider businesses and some high level manpower are migrants in Nigerians.

Implications from the two effects

From the data on Nigerian migrants in other countries, migrants in Nigeria from other countries and out flow and inflow of remittances, it is unequivocal that migration has greater influence in Nigeria economy. Capital is really one of the major obstacles of

development of a developing economy such as Nigeria. Just as Nigerians in Diaspora remit cash to families, relations and friends, so also do non-Nigerians in Nigeria do. The data in table 6 showed that more remittance leave Nigeria than it flows. The movement of both large quality human and physical capital outside Nigeria is a thing of worry. The colossal loss of academics, educationists, doctors, lawyers, engineers, economists, entrepreneurs and other professionals through migration presupposes that remittance is not sufficient to compensate for it. The decline in quality of Nigerian graduates can be attributed apart from lack of learning facilities, but to brain-drain or migration. Although the remittances contribution to GDP is meaningful, in our perception from all the aforementioned facts and figures, it is less meaningful than what leaves the economy.

Way forward

Notwithstanding remittances contribution to Nigerian economy, it is our stance that Nigeria has to do something to minimize frequent loss of scarce capital resources (human and physical) through migration. This on the ground that the negative effect of migration in our perception outweigh the positive effects, and also given the fact that remittances do not add to public revenue or support public expenditure. But taxes of individuals and businesses impact on the public revenue which in turn affect developmental expenditure. In order to reduce all form of migration in Nigeria, the following is expected to play enormous role:

- i. Revamping both the rural and urban environment, reforming social amenities and upgrading and maintenance of infrastructural requirement of the society to ensure sufficient and timely distribution of resources in the country. The unevenness of development of the rural area vis-à-vis urban areas can be altered through sufficient attention to making life conducive and promoting more investment and production in the rural areas of the country.
- ii. (ii) Insecurity and frequent crisis such as group agitations, religious disharmony, crimes, Boko Haram insurgence among others must be addressed. Many Nigerians have resorted to migration to various parts of the country and outside the country as a result of internal crisis. This requires more attention be focused on harmonious co-existence of all and sundry, and intensification of protection of all lives and property.

- iii. Condition of service for all categories of workers both the local, state and federal need to be urgently harmonized. Inequality in income of people with similar qualification and skill serving at different tiers of the government should be put to an end. Good atmosphere for operation cum the materials required by the academics, doctors, nurses, lawyers, architects, economists among others to enable them put in their best must be provided. This implies annihilation of brain-drain and improving reward system commensurate to input. It equal calls for reducing cost of governance to enable more funds to be available to restructure the economy for better.
- iv. Institutions of learning and health centres must be properly staffed and equipped. Nigeria has to practically and conscientiously emulate or adopt pattern of education system, management of students and staff as it is obtainable in Japan, United Kingdom, United States among others. The colossal sum of hard currency spent by Nigerians in the pursuit of education and health care outside Nigeria is enough to reform Nigerian education system for effective knowledge impartation and service delivery.
- v. Nigeria should work frantically to industrialise so as to reduce over reliance on exportation of raw materials so as to increase aggregate economic activity and bring about more employment of resources.
- vi. Good governance is essential at the moment such as strict adherence of the rule of law, freedom of speech, freedom of association avoidance of nepotism, equitable distribution of societal resources, giving all the opportunity to be part of leadership and strict compliance with respect to federal character in all facets of the economy.

CONCLUSION

This paper has examined and reviewed the effects of migration and remittances in Nigeria over the years. It was obvious that remittances from migrants have tremendously impacted on the Nigerian economy but it was perceived to be below the impact the Nigerians in Diaspora would have, have supposing the working environment was conducive for them to remain and work in Nigeria. This view is supported by the perception of the Deputy Executive-Secretary of the Economic Commission for Africa who posits that the exodus of African experts to the West is one of the

greatest barriers to Africa's progress and that African leaders have a major obligation to ensure that professionals remain in the continent; or else, in 25 years' time, Africa will be empty of brains (Sivia, 2007; Thalasa, 2010). It is the stance of the authors that more development and better living standard is possible in Nigeria if the abundance human capital outside the country are made to stay and contribute their quota to aggregate economic activity through revamping and restructuring the economy for better economic activities that can provide good working environment and give job opportunities to the teeming unemployed.

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